

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Resolving three-dimensional wind velocity fields with sequential wind-Doppler LiDAR for wind energy in the complex terrain - Gotthard Pass, Switzerland

[version 1; peer review: 1 approved with reservations, 2 not approved]

Brandon van Schaik ^{1,2}¹Laboratory of Cryospheric Sciences, Environmental Engineering Institute, Ecole polytechnique federale de Lausanne (EPFL), Sion, Valais, 1950, Switzerland²Snow Processes, Swiss Institute for Snow and Avalanche Research (SLF), Davos, Graubünden, 7260, Switzerland

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Abstract

Background

Understanding the effects of the complex terrain on wind turbines in alpine regions requires high-resolution computational modelling accompanied by detailed wind observations. In technologically advanced measurement campaigns, often multiple synchronised wind-Doppler LiDARs are deployed to overcome the limitation of these instruments to only measure line-of-sight velocity.

Methods

In this work, a novel deployment method, a sequential wind-Doppler LiDAR deployment is introduced. We present the example of a field campaign on the Gotthard Pass, a narrow north-south permutated high-mountain pass in the central Swiss Alps. We propose a matching algorithm that can robustly group wind profiles, enabling comparable scientific detail to study turbine efficiency as in synchronised triple LiDAR campaigns, whilst only requiring a single LiDAR instrument to be deployed.

Results

In the three-month study period in the summer of 2023, we successfully used turbulence kinetic energy, wind shear and veer, as

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- Norman Wildmann**, Institut für Physik der Atmosphäre, Oberpfaffenhofen, Germany
- Shengming Tang** , Shanghai Typhoon Institute of China Meteorological Administration, Shanghai, China
- Nikolas Angelou** , Technical University of Denmark (DTU), Frederiksborgevej, Denmark
- Feng Guo** ,

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well as wind channelling to explain turbine power production discrepancies observed in the five turbines erected on a mountain pass.

Plain Language Summary

We have developed a new method of using an existing measurement device to improve the information we can gather about the changes in the wind as they pass over a mountain pass. Five wind turbines were constructed in 2020 on top of a prominent Swiss mountain pass in the Gotthard Wind Park. It is known that these mountain winds are much stronger due to an effect called wind channelling, allowing the wind turbines to generate more energy. With our new measurement method, we can visualise the airflow through the wind park with just one sensor by applying an algorithm that can identify similar wind conditions at different times. Our measurement campaign during the Summer of 2023 allowed us to study several different flow patterns and identify some complex flow structures that affect the efficiency of the wind turbine. We show for each turbine, specifically for Northerly and Southerly winds, how efficient their energy production is, and explain with our detailed wind flow measurements, how these can arise due to the surrounding mountains.

Keywords

wind, energy, complex terrain, lidar, wind turbine, shear, turbulence, turbulence kinetic energy, wind turbine efficiency, wind channeling, stratification, atmosphere, Gotthard, Switzerland

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Corresponding author: Brandon van Schaik (brandon.vanschaik@epfl.ch)

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Introduction

Exact and reliable measurements of the three-dimensional wind are paramount for wind energy potential calculations for the design of wind farms. Wind measurements in complex terrain are much more challenging than over flat terrain due to the increased complexity of wind patterns both horizontally and vertically. The complex terrain, in a wind energy assessment (WEA) context, refers to an area with varied and intricate orographical features that can significantly impact wind flow patterns. Complex terrain often includes diverse landscape elements such as hills, valleys, ridges, cliffs, boulders, trees, or human infrastructure irregularities such as buildings or wind turbines that can cause complex interactions with the incident wind¹. In WEA, understanding and quantifying the effects of complex terrain is crucial because these features can lead to variations in wind speed, wind direction, and turbulence, influencing the performance of wind turbines by reducing or augmenting their efficiency².

In Switzerland, the consideration of complex terrain for WEA is particularly pertinent. Policymakers have shown their intentions to phase out nuclear energy sources and transition to a fully renewable energy strategy by 2050³, which was approved by the public referendum on 21 May 2017. In a 2022 report by the Swiss Federal Office of Energy, it was concluded that nearly half of Swiss wind energy potential is located in the alpine region⁴. This amount becomes even more impressive when the issues related to alpine wind energy are highlighted: 1) the logistics of wind turbine construction in the mountains is more challenging and costly^{5,6}, 2) the endangerment of wildlife, and especially bird species can be unacceptable in some regions⁷, 3) social acceptance in the form of nature and wilderness zoning, including natural horizon objections can limit wind turbine projects to several kilometres away from settlements and mountain roads or trails^{6,8}. The recent construction of several wind parks in the complex terrain of the Alps emphasises the imperative for further detailed studies in this domain. The present study focuses only on the physical aspects of wind potential assessment, not on ecological and social acceptance issues.

Methods

LiDAR studies in the complex terrain

Several extensive field experiments addressing flows in the complex terrain have been conducted in the past twenty years. In 2007–2008, the Bolund experiment, ~25 km East of Copenhagen, Denmark, set the benchmark for experimental complex terrain studies using remote sensing applications such as wind-Doppler Light Detection and Ranging (LiDAR). This small 300 m wide mesa-shaped island with slopes on all directions exceeding 30° surrounded by a large body of water serves as an idealised example of showcasing the effects of terrain features on the wind⁹. The hill was covered with 10 meteorological masts (MET-mast) ranging between 20 and 150 m in height, with a LiDAR on the far end of the peninsula and a LiDAR 300 m away on the leeward side of the hill. Based on the 60-day experimental campaign, CFD simulations were validated to understand the exact flow over the terrain feature up to 150 m above ground level (a.g.l.)¹⁰.

Although the Bolund experiment provides the benchmark for simulations¹¹ and data of high-resolution wind profiles¹² for WEA, the peninsula does not accurately represent more complex terrain such as alpine environments.

A more advanced complex terrain study in 2015–2017, specifically aimed at WEA was carried out in Perdigoão, ~150 km northeast of Lisbon, Portugal¹³. Here, two parallel hill ridge lines, separated by approx. 1500 m are covered with wind turbines. Over the three years, various measurement campaigns were held including multiple wind-Doppler LiDARs, which were used in conjunction to project three-dimensional wind velocity fields throughout the entire valley^{14,15}. Additionally, an airborne LiDAR was used to measure wind transects along the valley¹⁶. Both long-term studies of the meso-scale wind profile for WEA have been validated with LiDAR data^{17,18}, as well as much smaller-scale turbine wake simulations^{19,20}, proving the validity of LiDAR measurements over a wide range of spatial resolutions.

In the largest instances of complex terrain wind studies such as the Meso-scale Alpine Project (MAP)²¹ have defined the state-of-the-art for the past 20 years. Although the study lacks specific wind energy analyses, the project serves as the basis for the validation of numerical weather prediction models in highly complex terrain^{22–25}.

Such large-scale wind energy projects provide a wealth of detailed observational data available for high-resolution simulations of their respective study areas, however not all WEA studies merit and require such large investments. WEAs rarely operate more than one LiDAR to perform a wind energy assessment.

Single LiDAR experiments have proven to be capable of forecasting short-term wind fluctuations²⁶, as well as suitable for CFD model validation in complex terrain^{27–29}. Kristianti *et al.* 2023³⁰ investigated the complex alpine sites of Les Diablerets and the Lukmanier Pass, both representative of the Swiss Alps, in a comparative study to estimate the wind energy potential at these locations. Here a novel approach pioneered the use of artificial neural networks to combine weather station data with limited wind-Doppler LiDAR measurements to improve WEA. Additionally, the use of a machine learning model, called Wind-Topo³¹, which forecasts 10 m a.g.l. wind speeds at 53 m resolution, was coupled to 100 m a.g.l. wind speeds measured by the LiDAR system using a specific transfer function. Although this transfer function could not yet be validated in a general alpine context, it proves the potential for the combination of different data sources to improve complex terrain WEA without increasing investment costs massively.

State-of-the-art in the industry

The prevalence of terrestrial remote sensing techniques, such as LiDAR experiments, has significantly advanced the ability of WEA in scientific communities. Despite their popularity, conventional MET-masts equipped with anemometers extending up to at least two-thirds of the projected turbine hub height remain the industry standard. This preference is attributed in part

to the advantage of obtaining a single-point three-dimensional wind measurement³², a feature challenging for LiDAR systems, especially in complex terrains where horizontal wind continuity and uniformity cannot be guaranteed within the scanning cone³³. Conversely, the assumption that is made to extrapolate MET-mast measurements from two-thirds of the turbine hub height to a complete profile over the swept area by the turbine blade, usually by logarithmic wind profile theory, cannot be applied to extreme complex terrain locations³⁴.

While the concept of employing multiple LiDARs appears promising in addressing this challenge, practical issues persist in installation, maintenance, data analysis, cost and instrument availability^{35–37}. These complexities demand an advanced understanding of the instruments and the environmental conditions, consequently contributing to elevated operational costs. Moreover, the construction expense, impracticality of installing MET-masts in mountainous regions combined with severe weather and increased risk of natural hazards further underscore the need for alternative approaches³⁸.

In response to these challenges, remote sensing methodologies employing a single wind-Doppler LiDAR have gained traction as a cost-effective and efficient alternative. In certain scenarios, sound-wave-based alternatives like Sonic Detection and Ranging (SoDAR) have been explored^{39,40}, albeit infrequently. This is primarily due to the limitations in range and concerns about noise pollution associated with SoDARs, positioning single LiDAR WEA methodologies as the most logical step forward for prospective wind parks⁴¹.

Additionally, an argument can be made for the use of LiDAR profilers instead of free-scanning LiDARs. A LiDAR profiler is designed for measuring vertical atmospheric profiles, emitting laser pulses in fixed directions, often in a conical shape, to capture wind data at a range of altitudes after which it combines the line-of-sight velocities captured in different directions to provide a volume-averaged three-dimensional wind speed of the cone swept by the laser. In contrast, a free-scanning LiDAR can point its laser beam in any direction of a hemisphere following predefined scan patterns, providing more freedom in choosing the line-of-sight wind speeds that are to be measured by the laser beam. This freedom does come at the cost that an experienced user is required to program the suitable scanning patterns and to analyse the data, particularly in the complex terrain. The cost of free-scanning LiDARs is nearly three times higher than that of a LiDAR profiler further limiting the incentive for prospective investors to choose this option. Additionally, the free-scanning LiDAR are heavier, more delicate, and have higher power demands, which limits the range of deployment in the complex terrain drastically.

The Gotthard sequential LiDAR transect experiment

It is for these reasons that in this study, we introduce a novel approach employing a *sequential LiDAR* transect experiment utilising a single wind-Doppler LiDAR profiler. The applicability of this methodology is demonstrated in a specific case study focused on a wind farm located on the Gotthard Pass (46.55°N, 8.56°E, 2106 m a.s.l.) connecting the northern and

southern alpine regions in Switzerland. Since October 2020, the upper plateau of the pass has been home to five wind turbines, forming the basis of our investigation and providing wind energy data for validation.

This work serves as a proof of concept and as a preliminary showcase of the unique data sets and analyses that are unlocked by the sequential LiDAR experimental methodology, enabling the high-resolution study of the three-dimensional wind over the entire wind park domain.

In Section 2, we provide a detailed description of the Gotthard Pass environment and the wind park site, emphasising the existing and additionally installed study-specific instrumentation used. Sections 3 and 4 outline the methodology of the sequential LiDAR transect experiment, and propose a novel method to analyse sequential LiDAR experiments. Section 5 highlights the unique wind flow over the sequential LiDAR transect including the site-specific and temporal evolution of wind profiles over the complex terrain for the Gotthard wind park, exploring the effects of the complex terrain on the air-flow in the wind park and how this affects turbine performance. Section 6 discusses and concludes on the efficacy of the sequential LiDAR method in view of logistical challenges and key findings of this experiment providing an outlook into the implications to future WEA studies.

Field site and instrumentation

The Gotthard wind park is situated atop the Gotthard Pass at an elevation of 2106 m a.s.l. in the Swiss Alps, at approximately 46.55°N latitude and 8.56°E longitude. [Figure 1](#) shows the Gotthard region with 100 m elevation contour lines, the Gotthard wind park turbines (red diamonds), the topographical points of interest (blue), towns (green triangles) and the surrounding weather stations (orange triangles). This pass is a saddle point between the Northern Urseren valley from the town Andermatt, canton Uri (approximately 1440 m a.s.l.) and the Southern Bedretto valley at the town of Airolo, canton Ticino (approximately 1210 m a.s.l.). From the Urseren valley, the pass ascends over a distance of 6.8 km along a near-north facing slope with an aspect of 7° up to the summit of the Gotthard Pass. This Upper Reuss valley is characterised by an average slope of 5.6° with minimal deviation and few obstacles to obstruct the wind flow. Subsequently, the pass descends over a distance of 4.3 km along a South-East facing slope with an aspect of 147° called the Tremola valley, featuring an average slope of 12.1°. From the village of Hospental to Airolo, the pass curves gradually towards the East with a radius of curvature of 7.5 km.

The central location of the Gotthard Pass is most frequently a major weather divide for the Northern and Southern Alps. Its north-south orientation provides its distinctive and characteristic feature of exhibiting both North and South Föhn winds, thus often experiencing increased wind flow on the respective lee side of the pass increasing wind energy potential³⁰.

Continuing with [Figure 1](#), the contours of the mountain pass are indicated. The southern valley, colloquially known as the

Figure 1. Topographical overview of the Gotthard region.

Tremola valley, is notably narrower compared to its northern counterpart, with a transverse distance of approximately 300 m at an elevation of 100 m above the valley floor. In contrast, the Northern valley is wider with a valley width of 500-750 m at the 100 m above the valley floor. Moreover, the Tremola valley showcases an orographic prominence, indicated on [Figure 2](#) (orange marker), the Scara Orello mountain (2242 m a.s.l.), located 2 km southeast of the upper plateau, blocking the free-flowing streamline of air over the eastern side of the pass in southerly winds. This situation will be discussed in more detail later. To the East and the West of the saddle point, prominent mountains reaching up several hundred meters above the upper plateau shelter the wind park from easterly and westerly winds, in fact, they are responsible for the flow channelling customarily observed in the Gotthard wind park.

Zooming in on the Gotthard wind park itself ([Figure 3](#)), the Gotthard wind park comprises five turbines positioned on the upper plateau. These turbines are numbered sequentially from North to South, with Turbines 1, 2, 4, and 5 situated on the western side, while Turbine 3 occupies the eastern side. The surrounding landscape features boulders of up to 15 m tall, several small lakes, and grass patches as visible in [Figure 2](#). Notably, the treeline is located far below the upper plateau and thus does not significantly influence the wind flow in the wind park itself. To the Southeast of Turbine 3, a small

Figure 2. The Gotthard Pass in summer seen from the northwestern side of the Upper Plateau.

settlement consisting of low buildings and shelters is observed, exhibiting a similar surface roughness to the boulders present elsewhere on the upper plateau by estimate.

Instrumentation overview

The five wind turbines in the Gotthard wind park are Enercon E92 turbines with a blade diameter of 92 m mounted upon a 98 m mast. They are specified for 2.35MW rated power, and a cut-in, rated, and cut-out wind speed of 2 m/s, 11 m/s, and 25 m/s, respectively. [Table 1](#) provides details regarding the

Figure 3. The Gotthard Upper Plateau, featuring wind turbines (red diamonds), LiDAR locations (orange dots), and the camera perspective of Figure 2.

geographical coordinates, elevation, and characteristics of these turbines, as well as all instrumentation employed in this study. Firstly, the sequential LiDAR data set includes wind profiles at twenty range gates focused around the turbine height of the wind park, starting with range gates at 40 m up to 160 m increasing by steps of 10 m. After which, the range gates increase by steps of 20 m up to 300 m, to cover wind speeds well above the wind turbines to provide a comprehensive wind profile of the wind park. A range gate is a specific range interval from the LiDAR instrument within which it measures the wind speed and direction by analysing the Doppler shift of the returned signal within this interval.

This large array of wind profiles is complemented by both wind speed and power metrics from individual turbines, which are made available by the turbine operators, Azienda Elettrica Ticinese, for this study to validate and compare the LiDAR profiles along the transect.

Data from eleven mountain weather stations, operated by the Swiss Institute for Snow and Avalanche Research (SLF)⁴², and three weather stations in the vicinity of the Gotthard Pass, and on a nearby wind park at similar elevation, operated by

the Swiss Federal Office for Meteorology and Climatology (MeteoSwiss)⁴³ are extracted around the Gotthard Pass to complement the meteorological data collected during this campaign.

Sequential LiDAR methodology

To analyse the evolution of wind patterns across the complex terrain of the Gotthard wind park, a sequential LiDAR transect was executed. This transect, conducted over three months from 19 June to 20 September 2023, focuses on the upper plateau where the mountains slopes channel the prevailing wind in downwind direction. The transect includes nine distinct LiDAR locations, positioned at regular increments, plus one additional deployment near Turbine 3 on the eastern side of the plateau. This LiDAR transect aims to provide an extensive collection of wind profiles along the prevailing wind direction axis of the wind park, emphasising high-resolution, three-dimensional wind velocity fields unattainable through conventional single LiDAR deployments.

LiDAR details

The VAISALA WindCube v2.1 WLS7-1726 profiler was the sole remote-sensing wind measurement instrument used for this campaign, sequentially situated between the five turbines in the Gotthard wind park. The LiDAR recorded wind data at twenty discrete range gates with a width of 20 m, covering elevations from 40 m to 160 m in 10 m increments. Beyond 160 m, increments increased to 20 m, reaching up to 300 m above the local ground level.

The LiDAR profiler makes use of five pulsed laser beams, which are magnetically controlled by the instrument with 0.8 s of exposure in a vertical stare position after the instrument moves the laser in 0.2 s to its next positions: North, East, South, and West with 28° angle from the vertical axis with the same exposure time. The return signal of the 1543 nm, 30 mW mean power laser is recaptured, and based on the Doppler shift of the five line-of-sight laser beams a three-dimensional wind vector is determined for each range gate in the profile.

This specific instrument logs data at two temporal resolutions: one-second, individual beam data, as well as 10-min averaged data, which can be used for both relatively high-level wind profile and shear structure analysis as well as turbulence intensity calculations for WEA purposes. Both time resolution data sets are made available via the instructions in Table 1.

Sequential LiDAR transect

The LiDAR transect logistics involved the transport of the LiDAR by vehicle over the various wind turbine servicing roads. When the closest point to the sequential LiDAR position was reached, the LiDAR was carried up to 200 m away from infrastructure over rough terrain by two individuals. It was placed on a levelled wooden palette to minimize movement in soft soil and to protect against flooding. Power was accessed through extension cables up to 330 m long, connected to the grid via different wind turbines. The two extremes of the transect were defined by distances of -225 m and +1100 m from the

Table 1. Instrumentation and data availability.

Dataset	Station	Data access	Eastings [m]	Northing [m]	Altitude [m]	Period [ISO 8601, UTC]	Description
LiDAR transect	L1	Available via Zenodo DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14524723	2686269	1156520	2101	2023-06-19T16:20Z - 2023-06-21T22:50Z	Origin of transect
	L2		2686173	1156369	2116	2023-07-14T13:10Z - 2023-07-14T13:00Z	+150m along transect
	L3		2686074	1156747	2103	2023-07-14T13:20Z - 2023-07-21T10:50Z	+300m along transect
	L4		2685975	1156862	2110	2023-07-21T15:00Z - 2023-07-27T11:40Z	+450m along transect
	L5		2685885	1156869	2112	2023-07-27T17:50Z - 2023-08-08T13:00Z	+600m along transect
	L6		2685787	1157097	2097	2023-08-11T14:10Z - 2023-08-12T11:10Z	+750m along transect
	L7		2686362	1157400	2096	2023-08-18T16:20Z - 2023-08-29T11:10Z	-150m along transect
	L8		2686409	1156444	2089	2023-08-29T12:40Z - 2023-09-04T09:00Z	-225m along transect
	L9		2685567	1157235	2063	2023-09-04T17:50Z - 2023-09-12T08:30Z	+1100m along transect
	L10		2686324	1157325	2157	2023-09-12T13:00Z - 2023-09-20T00:00Z	Off transect near Turbine 3
Wind Turbines (AET)	T1	N/A	2685655	1157555	2140	2020-10-29T09:50Z - 2023-09-20T00:00Z	
	T2		2685668	1157159	2200	2020-10-08T16:00Z - 2023-09-20T00:00Z	
	T3		2686253	1157143	2219	2020-10-19T17:30Z - 2023-09-20T00:00Z	On west-facing slope
	T4		2685886	1156734	2236	2020-11-23T11:30Z - 2023-09-20T00:00Z	
	T5		2686251	1156372	2219	2020-11-16T17:40Z - 2023-09-20T00:00Z	
Weather stations (SLF)	BED1	Publicly available by request to WSL SLF IMIS	2682908	1154748	2963	2023-06-19T00:00Z - 2023-09-20T00:00Z	Mountain top (West)
	BED3		2683169	1149445	2101	2023-06-19T00:00Z - 2023-09-20T00:00Z	Bedretto valley (North facing)
	BED4		2681160	1153250	2305	2023-06-19T00:00Z - 2023-09-20T00:00Z	Bedretto valley (South facing)
	CAM1		2696885	1148709	2668	2023-06-19T00:00Z - 2023-09-20T00:00Z	Leventina valley (North facing)
	GOS3		2689425	1167908	2209	2023-06-19T00:00Z - 2023-09-20T00:00Z	Mountain ridge (North)
	LUK1		2703254	1163181	3040	2023-06-19T00:00Z - 2023-09-20T00:00Z	Mountain top (East, far)
	OBW1		2666706	1155765	2733	2023-06-19T00:00Z - 2023-09-20T00:00Z	Mountain top (West, far)
	URS1		2691804	1169246	2784	2023-06-19T00:00Z - 2023-09-20T00:00Z	Mountain top (North)
	URS2		2682405	1160066	2169	2023-06-19T00:00Z - 2023-09-20T00:00Z	Urseren valley (North facing)
	VAL1		2689900	1156001	2450	2023-06-19T00:00Z - 2023-09-20T00:00Z	Tremola valley (Eastern mountain top)
	VAL2		2690126	1155980	2628	2023-06-19T00:00Z - 2023-09-20T00:00Z	Tremola valley (South facing)
	Weather stations (MeteoSwiss)		ANT	Publicly available by request to MeteoSwiss	2687445	1165044	1435
AIR		2690019	1153645		1157	2023-06-19T00:00Z - 2023-09-20T00:00Z	South exit of Gotthard pass (Airolo)
GUE		2690087	1167480		2286	2023-06-19T00:00Z - 2023-09-20T00:00Z	Mountain ridge Güttsch (North, 1 km)

origin, with the former constrained by a highway crossing and the latter avoiding potential wake interference from Turbines 1 and 2.

A radiation-shielded combined pressure, temperature, and humidity sensor was placed near the LiDAR 1 m above the ground. This sensor provides 10-minute averaged atmospheric variables at the LiDAR site. The LiDAR wind profiles could be monitored remotely via a 4G connection using the LTE network available on the Gotthard Pass, and the data was extracted on a near-weekly basis when the LiDAR was moved to its new position.

In some cases, data gaps are observed within the LiDAR transect which occurred due to disconnection or power loss from the grid from which the LiDAR was powered. In particular, heavy thunderstorms and hail storms which are common in the Swiss high-alpine region were prone to shutting down the LiDAR measurements. Due to long access time to the study area, the LiDAR sometimes could not be serviced promptly after shutdown further extending the data gaps.

The nine sequential LiDAR locations, spaced at 150 m increments, mostly covered the western part of the wind park. The orientation of the transect was based on the prevailing wind direction extracted from the Swiss Wind Atlas providing wind rose information at 100 m above the ground level, at 100 m horizontal and 25 m vertical resolution⁴⁴. Additionally, a tenth LiDAR location near Turbine 3 on the eastern side aimed to capture representative wind profiles from the eastern sector.

Sequential LiDAR inter-comparison

The primary challenge in analysing sequential LiDAR measurements lies in addressing the inherent lack of spatio-temporal continuity within the data set. As the weather is dynamic throughout the three-month measurement campaign, a method of inter-comparison of the different LiDAR deployments along the transect becomes imperative.

The method presented in this work involves the wind velocity measured on the nacelles of the five turbines situated on the upper plateau. By considering the wind vectors measured at the nacelles of each turbine, similar inflow characteristics can be deduced from which these common time frames can be compared over the entire sequential LiDAR study to show the evolution of wind profiles along the upper plateau.

These nacelle wind velocities are collected by anemometer stations installed on the nacelle, located at 98 m above ground level. These stations measure average wind speed and direction at 10-minute intervals, but do not include a measure for turbulence intensity. Within the time domain of the sequential LiDAR campaign, the horizontal wind speed components U and V are calculated for the total of 13'295 10-minute intervals covering the entire campaign period.

As shown in Figure 5, the vectorial difference in wind speed for each turbine is evaluated for each pair of 10-minute intervals

(i.e., $5 \cdot 13'295^2/2 \approx 4.4 \cdot 10^8$ pairs are evaluated) in the data set (Equation 1).

$$\begin{bmatrix} \Delta V_{ij}^{T_1} \\ \Delta V_{ij}^{T_2} \\ \Delta V_{ij}^{T_3} \\ \Delta V_{ij}^{T_4} \\ \Delta V_{ij}^{T_5} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} |\vec{v}_i^{T_1} - \vec{v}_j^{T_1}| \\ |\vec{v}_i^{T_2} - \vec{v}_j^{T_2}| \\ |\vec{v}_i^{T_3} - \vec{v}_j^{T_3}| \\ |\vec{v}_i^{T_4} - \vec{v}_j^{T_4}| \\ |\vec{v}_i^{T_5} - \vec{v}_j^{T_5}| \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{match}(\vec{v}_i^{Lx_1}, \vec{v}_j^{Lx_2}) = i \Leftrightarrow j = \max_{T_x \in \{T_1, T_2, T_3, T_4, T_5\}} \Delta V_{ij}^{T_x} \leq V_{margin} \quad (2)$$

Where $\vec{v}_i^{T_x}$ and $\vec{v}_j^{T_x}$ are turbine nacelle wind velocities at time interval i and j , respectively, for turbine $T_{x \in \{1,2,3,4,5\}}$. If all five turbines exhibit a wind velocity within the given error margin V_{margin} (Equation 2), the pair is considered to be a match. These matches are used later in the analysis to inter-compare LiDAR profiles at different time periods which were measured with sufficiently similar wind conditions.

As an example of the results from a matching algorithm, consider Figure 4. Here, four arbitrary 10-minute time intervals are chosen as timestamps. These timestamps are location-independent and therefore could be taken from anywhere along the sequential LiDAR transect. Note that according to the matching algorithm, any timestamp will always match with itself and is therefore disregarded (grey squares in figure). Time interval #1 does not match with any of the other time intervals, whereas time interval #4 matches with #2 and #3. Note that time intervals #2 and #3 do not necessarily have to match for #4 to have a match with both of them. This can happen if one or more wind vectors from the turbine nacelles are on the opposite sides of the velocity margin as shown in Figure 5 for Turbines 1 and 5 where the green and yellow vectors are within the blue error margin but not within the margin of each

Matched timestamps = (75%) 3 out of 4	Time interval #1	Time interval #2	Time interval #3	Time interval #4	Max(N)
	Time interval #1	No Match	No Match	No Match	
Time interval #2	No Match	No Match	No Match	Match	1
Time interval #3	No Match	No Match	No Match	Match	1
Time interval #4	No Match	Match	Match	No Match	2

Figure 4. Example table of a matching algorithm where the timestamps are matched.

Figure 5. Schematic of the matching algorithm, visualize three different snapshots by coloured vectors.

other. Finally, this table is symmetric and therefore only half of the computations must be performed to complete the algorithm.

To find the optimal value for V_{margin} , five different error margins were tested as shown in Table 2, where the resulting matches are shown for several values for V_{margin} . Based on the mean wind speed observed in the wind park $\bar{V}_{windpark} = 4.95$ m/s a margin of $V_{margin} = 0.5$ m/s $\approx 0.1 \bar{V}_{windpark}$ is chosen because of its balance between number of matches and relatively small error margin having identified 6'006 timestamps that hold at least one match. It should be noted that wind speeds ≤ 0.5 m/s are very rare, only observed in 3.6% of the data, and these low wind speed matches are disregarded due to the error margin being too large, creating inaccurate matches. The largest match includes 29 10-minute snapshots over several LiDAR locations. However, this also guarantees that some 10-minute snapshots are in the same LiDAR location, and one of these has to be chosen per LiDAR location in any particular visualisation.

Comparison of five error margins V_{margin} with their respective number of timestamps involved in a match as well as the largest collection of timestamps in a single match for various values of V_{margin} .

Using the velocity margin of $V_{margin} = 0.5$ m/s, the measured LiDAR profiles can now be inter-compared. Since the matching algorithm described above only requires the wind turbine wind velocity data points, there are several cases where the timestamp does not have a corresponding LiDAR wind profile due to LiDAR data gaps. In fact, 4'040 of the 6'006 matches have LiDAR data available for at least two wind profiles ($\vec{v}_i^{L_{x_1}}$ & $\vec{v}_j^{L_{x_2}}$) from the matched timestamps to make inter-comparison possible (Equation 3).

$$\exists \vec{v}_i^{L_{x_1}}, \vec{v}_j^{L_{x_2}} \mid L_{x_1}, L_{x_2} \in \{L_1, L_2, \dots, L_{10}\}, L_{x_1} \neq L_{x_2}, i \leftrightarrow j \quad (3)$$

Table 2. Comparison of V_{margin} and the number of matches that are created.

V_{margin}	Matched timestamps	max(N)
2.0 m/s	98.6% (13'112)	2'757
1.0 m/s	92.9% (12'346)	444
0.5 m/s	45.2% (6'006)	29
0.2 m/s	<0.01% (84)	3
0.1 m/s	<0.001% (4)	1

Where L_{x_1} and L_{x_2} indicate two unique LiDAR locations, for both of which the LiDAR profiler has measured a wind velocity at the matched time interval i . It should be noted that Equation 3, describes only the minimum requirement for a match to be formed, in many cases more than two different LiDAR positions are in the same match, and multiple time intervals can exist for the same LiDAR position (Equation 4). However, such a match for i does not necessarily imply that j and k are also a match with each other, as their wind vectors could potentially be on the other side of the error margin (consider Turbine 1 in Figure 5).

$$match(\vec{v}_i^{L_{x_1}}, \vec{v}_j^{L_{x_2}}, \vec{v}_k^{L_{x_3}}) \rightarrow i \leftrightarrow j, i \leftrightarrow k \quad (4)$$

The distribution of these matched profiles, which include a multitude of LiDAR locations is shown in Figure 6. A large portion of matched timestamps only have one LiDAR location. This can be explained by the fact that many matches tend to happen between two timestamps within 30 minutes of each other, as the weather system has not changed significantly yet. However, there are still many matched wind profiles that are from different locations along the sequential LiDAR transect, with even two matches, which included at least one wind profile for seven different locations along the transect.

Variability in the LiDAR profile matching

To evaluate the robustness and variability of the proposed matching algorithm, we now consider “auto-matched” profiles, similar to Equation 4, with the only difference that the locations of L_{x_1} and L_{x_2} must now be equal. These profiles are constant in location, and only vary in time. Since these auto-matched profiles are matched, they are assumed to be similar in local weather conditions. As the topographical influences on the wind profile are constant for auto-matched profiles, they will become the subject of a robustness study to verify the validity of the proposed matching algorithm. In total, there are 3'778 auto-matched profiles originating from the ten LiDAR locations in the experiment. Assessing these auto-matched profiles regarding their consistency provides insight into the validity of regularly matched profiles along the transect by defining a reasonable standard deviation to the wind velocities and the turbulence kinetic energy. The matching algorithm described above collects LiDAR profiles for times when all wind turbines

Figure 6. Number of matches in the dataset for $V_{margin} = 0.5\text{m/s}$.

have similar wind flow patterns, within a 0.5 m/s error limit, and it can therefore be expected to have similar deviations in wind vectors of the auto-matched LiDAR profiles themselves. For all ten LiDAR locations, the auto-matched profiles are assessed based on their standard deviation in the three-dimensional wind vector as well as their turbulence kinetic energy (TKE). The TKE is calculated based on the LiDAR wind speed components U , V and W , and their respective standard deviations σ_U , σ_V and σ_W at 10-minute intervals in Equation 5. The WindCube v2.1 used in this experiment does not distinguish between σ_U and σ_V however, and opts for a $\sigma_{U_{horz}} = \sigma_U = \sigma_V$ instead. Although in this study, only the 10-minute interval LiDAR data is studied, the LiDAR measures a wind profile every 5 seconds, which is later averaged to form a more robust average. With the standard deviation of the line-of-sight wind speeds, a reasonable estimate for the turbulence intensity can be made at 10 minute intervals.

$$k = \frac{1}{2}(\sigma_U^2 + \sigma_V^2 + \sigma_W^2) \quad (5)$$

In Figure 7, the 68%, 95% and 99.7% quantiles of auto-matched LiDAR profiles are shown, which correspond to 1,2 and 3 standard deviations, respectively. From the standard deviation profiles shown in Figure 7, it can be observed that the majority of the auto-matched profiles are contained within the expected 0.5 m/s wind speed margin. However, in a small percentage of auto-matched profiles, the standard deviation in the wind speed does increase above V_{margin} . This effect is stronger at the lower and upper bounds of the LiDAR profile which are furthest away from the turbine nacelles at 98 m height. This effect is not observed in the turbulence kinetic energy, which is insensitive to height. This can be explained by the gradual reduction in turbulence as we move up in the atmospheric boundary layer, which balances out the continuous increase of turbulence kinetic energy in the range of the LiDAR profiles.

In addition to this, the introduction of vertical wind speed W to the wind vector \vec{v} increases the bias towards larger standard deviations in the wind speed; this is particularly visible for the 99.7% quantile. This can be explained by the fact that

the nacelle wind sensor only measures horizontal wind speed, and therefore the matching algorithm can not use the vertical wind component to assess whether two time intervals have similar vertical winds. Since this only becomes problematic for less than 1% of the matched profiles, a simple visual inspection of the three-dimensional wind field is sufficient to identify faulty vertical wind speed matches.

On the other hand, the atmospheric variables such as barometric pressure, air temperature and absolute humidity do not correlate well with the auto-matching algorithm and large variations can be observed, which indicates that the proposed matching algorithm is coherent in selecting similar wind flow patterns, but not in selecting similar weather conditions. This directly implies that atmospheric stability is also not necessarily constant throughout these matches. The lack of correlations in these atmospheric parameters can also be observed when using the atmospheric variables measured by the thirteen weather stations around the pass.

Thus, to analyse typical alpine wind events such as Föhn winds, which depend on humidity, air temperature, and pressure differences at both sides of a mountain, a deeper investigation into the atmospheric parameters for all timestamps involved in a match must be performed before such an event can be studied.

Results

Having established a robust matching algorithm for the sequential LiDAR measurements along the transect in the Gotthard wind park, the matched wind profiles can now be visualised along the transect, with all three wind components along the pass at any height of the measurement range. Previously, such visualisations were only possible using a triple wind-Doppler LiDAR setup with synchronised measurements.

Gotthard Pass wind characteristics

Firstly, the wind patterns observed on the pass at the height of the turbine nacelles are illustrated by wind roses in Figure 8. Here, northerly winds can be observed to be generally stronger than southerly winds. Particularly, wind speeds above the rated wind speed of the E92 turbine are much more prevalent. We define southerly winds as originating between the azimuths 75° and 255° and northerly wind from the remaining 180° sector. These distinct differences can be recognised in the Weibull distributions (Equation 6), which are split based on the two prevailing wind directions in Table 3.

$$f(v) = \frac{k}{A} \left(\frac{x}{A} \right)^{k-1} \exp - (x/A)^k \quad (6)$$

Wind roses at the nacelle height of each turbine based on 3 years of wind direction data.

Weibull parameters scale shape k [-] and A [m/s] parameters, and the measured mean wind speed $|\bar{v}|$ [m/s], split for northerly and southerly winds ($75^\circ < \theta \leq 255^\circ$) for the Gotthard wind turbines.

Figure 7. Quantiles of several wind parameters for all 3'778 auto-matched LiDAR profiles.

Figure 8. Wind roses of the five turbines in the Gotthard Wind Park.

In Figure 9, the wind roses at approximately 100 m above the ground of all the turbine and LiDAR locations are shown. The blue wind roses that are generated from LiDAR data do not exhibit the correct proportions in the frequency of the wind direction, as often only one week of data is available at

a given location. However, the wind roses illustrate the spatial progression of the general wind direction along the Gotthard wind park well. Particularly, the differences for northerly and southerly winds at any given location on the pass can be observed.

Transect wind profile evolution

Consider the northerly wind visualisation in Figure 10 and Figure 11, where one of the largest matches is visualised in side and top view, respectively. The seven LiDAR profiles were measured at different dates as well as time of day as indicated in Table 4. In the side view shown in Figure 10, the span of the wind turbine blades is indicated as red line. Since the transect runs through the western side of the Gotthard wind park, Turbines 1, 2, 4, and 5 are most relevant, whereas Turbine 3 is indicated with a dotted line as it is much further away from the transect and to the side. For the top view shown in Figure 11, the span of the turbines is indicated by a red circle with radius 46 m. Additionally, the tenth LiDAR profile is excluded from this side view of the transect as it is not located on the transect itself. For this wind profile, the top view of the Gotthard wind park in Figure 11 can be considered.

In Figure 10, the wind can be observed coming from the North with an upward wind component aloft, following the topography of the Reuss valley. As the wind moves over the wind park

plateau, the wind closer to the surface and around the turbine height becomes mainly horizontal and accelerates with L9 and L1 experiencing an average wind speed of 2.63 m/s and 3.59 m/s in the turbine blade swept area (approx.

Table 3. Weibull fit parameters of the Gotthard Wind Park for Northerly and Southerly winds.

Turbine	Northerly wind			Southerly wind		
	k	A	$ \bar{v} $	k	A	$ \bar{v} $
1	1.31	5.14	4.16	3.53	5.27	4.76
2	1.93	5.31	4.67	3.38	5.38	4.84
3	2.33	6.65	5.75	2.60	6.29	5.52
4	2.54	5.89	5.11	3.03	5.18	4.67
5	2.64	7.66	6.59	2.62	4.80	4.31

Figure 9. Spatial progression of wind direction over the Gotthard wind park, illustrated by wind roses at around 100 m above ground level.

Figure 10. Side view of a Northerly wind on the Gotthard Pass. Swept areas of turbine rotors are shown in red.

Figure 11. Top view of a Northerly wind on the Gotthard Pass. Height in meters is indicated by colour.

40–160m a.s.l.), respectively. This acceleration of the wind over the pass is generally observed for northerly winds. In L8, we observe a strong shear, and a decrease in average wind speed between 40–160m a.s.l. at 3.09 m/s, but the wind speed at the upper end is 44% higher than at the lower end of the turbine swept area. Furthermore, the wind vectors start curving downward as the flow approaches the Tremola valley, again following the terrain. This acceleration with northerly winds along the wind park can also be observed in the turbine energy output data: the southern Turbines 3 and 5 have a distinct increase in energy production for any medium to high northerly wind speed.

To explore other complex terrain wind phenomena that may impact turbine efficiency, not only the wind acceleration and

vertical wind speed components can be studied. Shear and veer evolution along the pass can often be observed, as well as three-dimensional turbulence intensities evolving over the wind park can be identified and visualised with the sequential LiDAR data set, as discussed in the following sections.

Wind shear and veer

For northerly wind, at the southern end of the transect, close to LiDAR location L8 (Figure 10), a clear shearing situation is visible. This shear is observed for any northerly wind over the Gotthard Pass, and is attributed to the small hill on which Turbine 5 is located. Similar shear patterns are observed around Turbine 5 for southerly winds, but they are less pronounced due to the sharp escarpment facing North, while it has a smoother South facing slope.

Table 4. LiDAR transect metadata of the match displayed in Figure 10 and Figure 11.

LiDAR	X_transect [m]	Date	Time [UTC]	Height range [m]
L8	-225	02.09.2023	17:50	40-300
L7	-150	N/A	N/A	N/A
L1	0	19.06.2023	18:30	40-300
L2	150	07.07.2023	08:40	40-300
L3	300	N/A	N/A	N/A
L4	450	23.07.2023	06:00	40-300
L5	600	28.07.2023	13:50	40-300
L6	750	12.08.2023	06:40	40-110
L9	1100	10.09.2023	13:40	40-240
L10	Off transect	N/A	N/A	N/A

In fact, for southerly winds a different orographic prominence, the Scara Orello mountain (2242 m) in the Tremola Valley (see Figure 2 and Figure 3), causes a much larger disturbance to the airflow over the Gotthard wind park. Consider Figure 12, where the top view of a southerly wind profile is visualised over the Gotthard Pass. The red vectors, between 250 and 300 m above ground are pointing in a north-westerly direction, whereas the vectors closer to the ground are pointing primarily north. This horizontal veering is attributed to the influence of the Scara Orello prominence, which stands at 140 m above the Gotthard wind park. The winds at higher altitudes, which can pass over the prominence are not affected much, and can therefore follow a straight streamline pointing northwest, as the lower Tremola valley has originally channelled the wind in this direction. The lower airflow is forced around the Scara Orello such that it then is redirected directly North over the pass.

This separation in the air layers around the turbine height at the Gotthard wind park is likely affecting the wind turbine

Figure 12. Top view of a southerly wind shear, most likely caused by the Scara Orello mountain.

performance of Turbines 5 and 4. Turbine 3 on the other hand, seems to be less affected by this wind veer as this turbine is located higher than the western turbines and reaches the upper air layer primarily. This horizontal stratification of the air can occasionally be observed by the eye such as in Figure 13, where low hanging clouds move around the Scara Orello and flow exclusively on the western side of the upper plateau, whereas the eastern part, where Turbine 3 is located, remains cloud-free.

Turbulence kinetic energy

Turbulence kinetic energy (TKE) k , Equation 5) exhibits bi-modal distributions, similar to the wind speed, along the LiDAR transect as shown in Figure 14.

For both northerly and southerly winds, the air enters the wind park at low turbulence levels. As the air moves further over the pass, the turbulence kinetic energy gradually increases. This is to be expected as the wind tends to accelerate on the upper plateau due to the increased density of streamlines as the air is pushed over the highest point of the pass and the overall kinetic energy of the wind increases, this will also contribute partly to the increased turbulence kinetic energy. Additionally, the surface obstacles, such as boulders, buildings and wind turbines will partly contribute to the increase of turbulence in the flow. For southerly winds in Figure 14(b), the increased turbulence in the lee of Turbine 5 can be observed in L1, L2 and L3 around the swept area of the turbine. This effect is not observed for northerly winds, which can be explained by the fact that these LiDAR locations are not directly in the lee of T2 and T4.

Near Turbine 3 on the eastern side of the pass measured by L10, the greatest turbulence kinetic energy can be observed for southerly winds. This correlates with the increased southerly wind speeds which were observed during the measurement period at this site. Additionally, the upwind terrain on this side of the pass is notably more complex, with the aforementioned

Figure 13. Indication by the cloud layer of the horizontal stratification for southerly winds due to the Scara Orello mountain (orange).

Scara Orello mountain (2242m) obstructing the wind for the western side of the pass. This will likely affect the flow on the eastern pass in a similar way.

We illustrate for the case of a symmetric deviation from a mean wind speed with deviation magnitude sigma, which is the average magnitude of deviations by definition, how the effect of non-linearity results in additional power that can be harvested. If we further assume that such a deviation gives the approximate magnitude of the power gain by turbulence, we can estimate the effective energy the turbulence holds for the type E-92 turbine on the Gotthard plateau. Consider the wind turbine power Equation 7:

$$P(v) = \frac{1}{2} \rho A v^3 \quad (7)$$

$\rho = 0.996 \pm 0.021 [kg/m^3]$ is the air density on the Gotthardpass, $A = \pi r^2 = 6650 [m^2]$ the swept area of a wind turbine, $v [m/s]$ the incident wind speed. Since the horizontal standard deviation of the wind for the WindCube is defined by $\sigma_u = \sigma_v = \sigma_{horz}$, we can consider a deviation σ_{horz} above and below the regular wind speed v . As the power scales with v^3 , the positive deviation increases the turbine power more than the negative deviation diminishes it. The difference in power due to this non-linearity is given in 8:

$$P_{turbulence} = \frac{P(v + \sigma_{horz}) + P(v - \sigma_{horz})}{2} - P(v) = \frac{3}{2} \rho A v \sigma_{horz}^2 \quad (8)$$

It should be noted that only a part of this turbulence kinetic energy can be transferred to the blades and therefore this value can only be used as an upper-bound. Additionally, this equation assumes that the wind speed deviations to the mean wind speed are symmetrical until the second order (e.g. normal distribution), the turbulence power can be considered only as a rough upper-bound to the influence of turbulence on the wind turbine performance. In the region between the cut-in wind speed and the rated wind speed, these turbulence contributions increase turbine power output. At lower wind speeds the turbine will not generate energy from this turbulence, and at higher wind speeds the positive effect $P(v + \sigma_{horz}) \rightarrow 0$, as the turbine does not generate additional energy as the power curve flattens. Finally, this equation assumes that the power is proportionally to the velocity cubed in the entire domain, which holds only between the cut-in and rated wind speeds of the turbine. Outside this domain, deviations will reduce as the power becomes constant with velocity.

Averaging over all locations and heights measured during the LiDAR campaign, combined with the all-time average wind speed in the Gotthard wind park of \bar{v} , we find that the northerly and southerly turbulence power upper-bound is 9.9kW and 16.2kW, respectively. Compared to the all-time average wind turbine power of 370.9kW, their respective positive contributions to power production can be estimated to be lower than 2.4% and 4.4%, respectively but it can increase to by multiple factors in exceptionally windy conditions and highly turbulent locations such as Turbine 3. However, it would

Figure 14. Log-normal fitted TKE distributions along the Gotthard pass. a) Northerly winds, b) Southerly winds, c) extended elevation profile.

be incorrect not to discuss that the existence of turbulence, in fact reduces the overall kinetic energy of the wind, thus a non-turbulent airflow would generate more wind energy. This perceived increase in power is only present because the nacelle-mounted anemometer can only sense the average wind speed at 10-min resolution, disregarding the turbulence variations in totality.

Regional weather correlations

Subsequently, based on the matching timestamps, the IMIS and SLF stations were assessed in an attempt to find correlations and patterns between the wind on the Gotthard Pass and other atmospheric variables in the vicinity of the pass. These correlations can be of interest in generalising the local high-resolution measurements to nearby locations, enabling an extended domain of the wind energy assessment. Additionally, potential correlations can help in future case studies to characterise specific weather systems from weather models to predict wind profiles around the study area itself.

Regarding the mountainside- and mountaintop-located IMIS stations, which measure at 1 hour resolution, no strong correlations ($|r| < 0.4$) can be found in any of the atmospheric variables and wind speed or direction compared to any data collected during the Gotthard 2023 campaign. The mountaintop stations provide moderately better correlations as they better represent the synoptic weather conditions and are less prone to small-scale local topographical effects. A simple model to predict northerly or southerly winds in the Gotthard wind park remains too challenging for simple linear correlation models, however. The mountainside stations generally had worse correlations ($|r| < 0.3$). This is attributed largely to the different slope aspects of the sites where the stations are located, far away from the Gotthard wind park itself.

The MeteoSwiss stations in the towns of Andermatt and Airolo provide a stronger correlation in form of temperature difference between the termini of the Gotthard Pass. This can be interpreted analog to the Föhn index on the northern and southern end of the pass, which is pre-calculated for a small amount of MeteoSwiss stations⁴⁵. During Föhn events, the temperature in the downwind valley is always observed to be higher than on the windward side at the same elevation, particularly during occurrences of stronger winds in the wind park. We chose to use the temperature difference between Airolo and Andermatt over the Föhn index in an attempt to study Föhn events, as it provides a continuously correlating variable to explain discrepancies in wind turbine efficiency, but also still encompasses northerly and southerly Föhn events. Additionally, since the matching algorithm does not necessarily perform well in combining similar regional weather conditions, the temperature difference remains as the most suitable choice.

Finally, the MeteoSwiss weather station Gütsch installed 11 km NNE of the Gotthard wind park, with an elevation of 180 m above the Gotthard wind park on an east-west ridgeline

provides the best data for this analysis. Although the wind components measured at Gütsch still lack correlation with those in the Gotthard wind park, barometric pressure, air temperature and humidity strongly correlate with the variables that were measured during at Gotthard Pass during the 2023 campaign. Particularly, temperature and pressure can be used to approximate their equivalence on Gotthard when our instruments are not present or had data gaps by using a lapse rate of $6.5^{\circ}\text{C per km}$ ($+1.7^{\circ}\text{C on Gotthard}$) and the barometric equation ($+17.42 \pm 0.36 \text{ hPa on Gotthard}$), respectively. The relative humidity is less correlating to that measured on Gotthard, however, since it is only used for estimating air density on the Gotthard Pass, for which it has a low sensitivity to errors, we assume the same humidity for both locations. This estimated air density is used to estimate the general turbine efficiency decrease, which can not be attributed to complex terrain interactions in the following section.

Wind turbine efficiency

The bi-directional wind system across the Gotthard is prevalent for the wind shear, wind veer and turbulence on the pass. The compound effects of these combine, and occasionally cancel, each other when the air parcels transfer their energy to the wind turbine blades. To study the impact of terrain and flow effects on the efficiency of the five wind turbines, the production power distributions for northerly and southerly winds are shown in [Figure 15](#). Wind speeds are selected between the cut-in speed and the rated wind speed, where the relation $P \propto v^3$ holds. In the range of $4 \text{ m/s} \leq v \leq 10 \text{ m/s}$, small disturbances and perturbations of the flow have the largest impact on power production. The power production is normalised to 7 m/s by the cubic relation between power and wind speed in this range.

Remaining in [Figure 15a](#), the central Turbine 4, generally experiences the benefits of the northerly and southerly winds equally with very low turbulence for both directions as well as moderate wind shear and veer only slightly reducing the turbine efficiency. Vertical wind components play almost no role for this turbine.

The most interesting sites are Turbines 5 and 3 during the campaign period, shown in [Figure 15a](#). These turbines not only benefit from flow acceleration for northerly winds, which generally bring higher wind speeds to this part of the pass. Remarkably, they can also transfer this energy more efficiently than expected when referring to the manufacturer's power curve when corrected for the reduced air density on the Gotthard Pass as a result of the elevation. This apparent out performance can be explained by the increased turbulence which reduces the average wind speeds to lower and unrealistic values due to the limitations of the nacelle-mounted anemometer, whilst the kinetic energy of the wind is higher than indicated. These effects are exaggerated most for the strong northerly winds which accelerate to much greater wind speeds before reaching these turbines due to the linear scaling with the average wind speed v , as shown by [Equation 8](#). The

Figure 15. Power generated by turbine and wind directions. (a) summer campaign period (19 June 2023 - 20 September 2023), (b) the entire dataset (October 2020 - September 2023). In Figure 15a where only the power data during the measurement campaign is shown, consider the northern Turbines 1 and 2. The southerly winds are more efficient at transferring energy to the wind turbine than their northerly counterparts. This discrepancy can be explained partly by the increased turbulence as the wind moves over the upper plateau before it reaches these turbines. For the northerly winds there is still a significant vertical wind speed component incident on the turbines increasing blade stresses and, making the programmed angle of attack of the turbine blades less efficient.

wind shear and wind veer for these northerly winds are already reduced to a minimum as observed for southerly winds for Turbines 1 and 2, and thus do not decrease the performance, whilst the strong shear and veer for southerly winds, as observed in Figure 12, has a detrimental effect on the power production. We do not observe the same apparent increase in power output due to turbulence for the northern Turbines 1 and 2 as generally, the wind speeds and turbulence are lower, therefore the effects are less pronounced.

During snow-covered periods, which are not included in our LiDAR measurement period, but are partly represented in the longer time domain of Figure 15b, a general decrease in efficiency is observed over all the turbines. This can likely be explained by the multiple meters thick snow layer covering the mountain pass for 7 months per year smoothing out the

terrain, reducing the apparent power increase by turbulence. The high performance of for example Turbine 3 and 5 is therefore reduced the greatest amount for northerlies, as it experienced the greatest discrepancies in summer time. There may be additional factors such as the presence of a much more stable atmospheric boundary layer due to the greatly reduced turbulent heat flux over the snow, resulting in more vertically stratified wind profiles that show more shear and veer and less turbulent airflow incident on the turbines. However, there is currently no data available to validate these speculations quantitatively.

Sequential LiDAR vs Synchronised LiDAR

The sequential LiDAR and synchronised LiDAR methods are both designed to provide three-dimensional wind fields over study areas. But their logistical and financial requirements, as well as data output quality differ.

The sequential LiDAR method requires a much smaller equipment budget. However, personnel costs are increased due to the logistical requirement of relocating the LiDAR instrument at regular intervals. Synchronised LiDAR methods require extensive planning in advance of the study as well as advanced knowledge on operating two or more LiDAR instruments in parallel, as well as post-processing the different datasets to form a three-dimensional wind field time series. The sequential LiDAR method requires less pre-campaign planning, and data post-processing.

Synchronised LiDAR systems can reach greater spatial resolution by employing multiple LiDARs, as well as extending the measured wind field to a greater domain, however it is still limited by the laser stare-time that is required to gain enough return photons to calculate a Doppler wind speed. Since wind energy assessments are generally based on 10-min average wind speeds, the state-of-the-art synchronised LiDAR systems can measure up to 300 unique points during this time interval⁴⁶. For the twenty range gates used in this study, such a synchronised LiDAR system comprising of three LiDARs could perform the transect measurements with 15 virtual sequential LiDAR profiles, whilst keeping much greater data availability as no matching algorithm is required.

Conclusion

This work presents a novel method for high-resolution three-dimensional wind profile measurements in complex terrain using a sequential spatially distributed LiDAR deployment. The project took place in the Gotthard wind park during the summer of 2023. The sequential LiDAR deployment is made along a transect on the western side of the upper plateau of the Gotthard Pass at an elevation of around 2100 m a.s.l., using a profiling VAISALA WindCube V2.1 wind-Doppler LiDAR instrument. The transect of nine sequential LiDAR locations and an additional tenth deployment on the eastern side of the pass aims to probe the entire wind park closely following the sites of five Enercon E92 wind turbines, constituting the high alpine Gotthard wind park. The Gotthard Pass is located in the centre of the Alps and features many topographical

effects and flow features typical of complex terrain that influence the wind profile that is incident on the wind turbines and which also can affect the performance of the latter. It is one of the few alpine passes that experiences both northerly and southerly Föhn winds, and wind channelling and acceleration over the pass is observed strongly as can be seen from the measured sequential LiDAR wind profiles.

A matching algorithm is proposed (Section 4) to allow for inter-comparison of LiDAR wind profiles measured at different moments in time, but for similar incoming wind conditions, verified by the meteorological observations on the nacelles of the five turbines. This matching algorithm is successful in identifying a large number of similar wind profiles throughout the three-month field campaign, with a maximum of seven wind profiles measured at different locations. The matching algorithm is independent of the location of the LiDAR wind profile, therefore the robustness of the algorithm has been verified by a statistical analysis of matching wind profiles at the same location, eliminating this unknown factor. With the statistical analysis, it can be concluded that the matching algorithm creates significant matches based on the incoming wind profiles within the error margin of 0.5 m/s in the wind velocity as specified, and therefore it can be used reliably to compare with LiDAR profiles from any other location in the sequential LiDAR deployment.

The sequential LiDAR data provides a unique visualisation of wind shear and wind veer along the alpine pass, as well as turbulence profiles clearly illustrating the complex terrain influences that impact wind turbine performance in mountainous applications (Sections 3, 5). We provide a qualitative overview of the complex terrain effects that significantly influence wind turbine performance, both in terms of potential drawbacks and benefits. Particularly, the stronger northerly winds exhibit acceleration over the pass, increasing wind energy production greatly for turbines furthest downwind. For upwind turbines, wind veer and shear decrease turbine performance, but this effect is reduced further downwind, where the channelling of the narrow pass plateau reduces these effects. The turbulence is largest on the eastern side of the pass, independent of the wind direction, which can be partly explained by the local terrain being rougher compared to the western part of the plateau. The presence of turbulence causes an apparent increase in wind turbine efficiency, which can actually be attributed to kinetic energy in the wind being transferred to turbulence instead of the average wind flow. The nacelle mounted anemometer only measures the average wind speed, but misses out on the short-term wind speed deviations which have a non-linear positive effect on the energy production of the turbines. A qualitative assessment of the compound effects of the complex terrain on the incident wind agrees well with the turbine data.

We hypothesize on effects during the typically 7 months lasting snow-covered winter period in the Gotthard wind park, where the thick snow pack smooths the terrain and reduces turbulence, which turbine data seems to indicate. In future work,

we plan to explore in more detail the effect of the presence of a smooth snow pack, which covers the wind park for 7 months of the year, as well as more complex interactions between air density and atmospheric stability outside of the summer period, and how this influences wind turbine performance. The current measurements in the region lack consistent and reliable atmospheric variables, requiring improved sensor coverage for this purpose.

Ethics and consent

Ethical approval and consent were not required.

Data availability

All data collected during the Gotthard experimental campaign are publicly available via Zenodo : Sequential Wind-Doppler LiDAR wind profile measurements on the Gotthard pass in Switzerland – Summer 2023, DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.14524723](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14524723)⁴⁷.

This project contains the following underlying data: Wind-Doppler LiDAR measurements along the transect in the Gotthard Wind Park.

This project contains the following underlying data:

- Gotthard_Transect_Experiment_STA_standard_Final.nc
- Opening_netCDF_4_formats.docx

Data are available under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International.

The authors have extracted weather data from MeteoSwiss and WSL SLF IMIS weather stations which are available upon request to the respective institutions. The wind turbine data made available by Azienda Elettrica Ticinese (AET) was shared with the authors under non-disclosure agreement for this research project.

One dataset that was used in our study has time-series data of wind power, wind speed and control algorithms of the wind turbines. This data was disclosed to the laboratory only under NDA. Readers, with interest for this data, can make a special request to the corresponding author after which the company will consider whether they will share this data under similar NDA conditions.

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to thank the Azienda Elettrica Ticinese (AET) as the providers of their wind turbine data for analysis in this project. We acknowledge the atmospheric data provided by MeteoSwiss via their IDAWEB portal and by SLF via the IMIS portal. Help and support from AET and EPFL is much appreciated, as well as the volunteers who enabled the realisation of the wind-Doppler LiDAR transect during fieldwork operations and troubleshooting. Finally, the authors thank Corentin Mottet and Jimmy Gasser for their analytical contributions to the data generated in this measurement campaign.

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Nikolas Angelou

Technical University of Denmark (DTU), Frederiksborgvej, Denmark

The manuscript entitled: "Resolving three-dimensional wind velocity fields with sequential wind-Doppler LiDAR for wind energy in the complex terrain – Gotthard Pass, Switzerland" presents a study of the wind conditions over a complex terrain. The topic is relevant in a wind energy context, since as it is also pointed by the authors, the wind resource assessment over complex terrain is a challenging task that requires wind observations. For this purpose, the authors performed a field study using a ground-based wind lidar profiler, which was sequentially moved to different locations, and developed a methodology to characterise the spatial variability of the wind conditions. Even though the topic is interesting the proposed methodology has the following weaknesses:

1. The wind lidar data set consists of observations acquired in different locations during a 3-month period. During such a period the wind conditions change, therefore it is not straightforward to inter-compare the wind profile acquired over one week in June in one location with the one measured in September in another location. Additionally, the measurement duration at each location varies from 1 to 12 days. This duration is quite limited and further as the authors state the measurements were acquired over different times of the day. Therefore, the measured wind profiles are not necessary characteristic of the wind conditions at the measured locations.
2. The matching algorithm proposed, which is one of the innovations of this study, is based on grouping the acquired wind lidar data set according to the hub-height wind speed measured by the nacelle-based anemometers. However, similar wind conditions at the hub-height do not necessary correspond to a specific wind profile. Furthermore, the application of this method requires the measurement of the wind conditions over different locations at the hub height of a wind turbine. Therefore, it cannot be used in the context of a wind resource assessment.
3. There is no discussion in the manuscript about the flow distortion of the nacelle-mounted anemometer and the reliability of the measurement of the longitudinal and transverse component of the horizontal wind vector.
4. The accurate measurement of the wind profile using a ground-based wind profile assumes of horizontal flow homogeneity. An assumption that is not valid over a complex terrain and

thus the derivation of the mean wind profile using a ground-based wind lidar profiler is not necessarily correct. This is even more relevant, when wind lidar profiler data are used to estimate the standard deviation of the wind vector components.

5. Based on the locations where the wind lidar measurements were acquired and the examined wind direction sectors, I imagine that at least part of the wind lidar measurements are biased by the wake generated by the wind turbines.

Based on the above points, I think that the statistical analysis performed is not appropriate and cannot support the conclusions drawn. Furthermore, the quality of the figures and the use of certain references should be improved/corrected (for example the reference [10] is not presenting a validation of a CFD simulation). Therefore, I unfortunately think that the article cannot be considered for indexing in its current version.

Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it cite the current literature?

Partly

Is the study design appropriate and does the work have academic merit?

No

Are sufficient details of methods and analysis provided to allow replication by others?

Yes

If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate?

No

Are all the source data underlying the results available to ensure full reproducibility?

Partly

Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the results?

No

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Wind Lidar, Wind Energy, Atmospheric Boundary Layer

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to state that I do not consider it to be of an acceptable scientific standard, for reasons outlined above.

Author Response 11 Nov 2025

Brandon van Schaik

[Nikolas Angelou](#)

1. The wind lidar data set consists of observations acquired in different locations during a 3-month period. During such a period the wind conditions change, therefore it is not straightforward to inter-compare the wind profile acquired over one week in June in one location with the one measured in September in another location. Additionally,

the measurement duration at each location varies from 1 to 12 days. This duration is quite limited and further as the authors state the measurements were acquired over different times of the day. Therefore, the measured wind profiles are not necessary characteristic of the wind conditions at the measured locations.

We acknowledge that the LiDAR measurements at each site are not necessarily representative of the full seasonal wind variability, nor are they sufficient to define a robust statistical wind distribution or wind rose for each location. However, the intent of this study is not to present a climatological analysis, but rather to investigate spatial variability and flow characteristics during the measurement period. In response to this comment, and those made by another reviewer, we have complemented the LiDAR observations with additional CFD simulations covering the full 3-month campaign period and the entire mountain pass. These simulations provide spatially and temporally continuous wind fields that support the short-term measurements. Specifically, we have identified 8 characteristic features including, global horizontal irradiance, atmospheric stability, vertical shear magnitude, variance of the vertical turbulence, an average of the transect wind field, and the synoptic wind at 5km. To this end, the Methodology section is completely overhauled and Results updated accordingly. We believe this addresses the reviewer's concern by providing a more complete picture of the wind conditions across all sites.

1. The matching algorithm proposed, which is one of the innovations of this study, is based on grouping the acquired wind lidar data set according to the hub-height wind speed measured by the nacelle-based anemometers. However, similar wind conditions at the hub-height do not necessary correspond to a specific wind profile. Furthermore, the application of this method requires the measurement of the wind conditions over different locations at the hub height of a wind turbine. Therefore, it cannot be used in the context of a wind resource assessment.

Thanks to your suggestions we have opted to provide additional CFD simulations to help contextualize the turbine wind vector matching algorithm. We have updated the matching algorithm as elaborated in the previous comments. We refer to the Methodology section of the manuscript for the detailed overview of the 8 characteristic features that are now implemented.

1. There is no discussion in the manuscript about the flow distortion of the nacelle-mounted anemometer and the reliability of the measurement of the longitudinal and transverse component of the horizontal wind vector.

Nacelle distortion is an important part when considering nacelle measured wind speed to wind power generated by the wind turbine. In this study we only ever consider nacelle measured wind speeds relative to measurements from the same anemometer in the same location of the same turbine. Therefore, this distortion is not relevant as the same bias is included in all comparisons and cancels out. With the new introduction of CFD simulations, this issue becomes valid in a hypothetical case where we compare CFD simulations to the nacelle measurement. We address in the manuscript that this distortion is present, and that it is not possible to directly compare them in this case. **Addressed in the manuscript as such:** *"We are unable to compare the HICAR wind vectors at the wind turbine nacelles with the in-situ data measured by the anemometers due to the flow distortion of the nacelle which is not simulated."*

1. The accurate measurement of the wind profile using a ground-based wind profile assumes of horizontal flow homogeneity. An assumption that is not valid over a complex terrain and thus the derivation of the mean wind profile using a ground-

based wind lidar profiler is not necessarily correct. This is even more relevant, when wind lidar profiler data are used to estimate the standard deviation of the wind vector components.

With the WindCube V2.1 profiler, the angled lasers are pointed 28° from the vertical. This roughly means that at 100m the N and S beam are ~100m apart. With our newly available CFD simulations we can now explore how much the wind vector has changed at 100m and 300m height with 100m and 300m horizontal spacing respectively in all 4 cardinal directions. Vertical inhomogeneity in both the N-S and E-W direction at corresponding the corresponding height above the LiDAR show the following biases and standard deviations:

100m above LiDAR

(100m horizontal spacing) Bias [m/s] Standard deviation [m/s] N – S differences in v (dir. north) 0.094 0.116 E – W differences in u (dir. east) 0.002 0.251 N – S & E – W differences in w (dir. up) 0.012 0.058

300m above LiDAR

(300m horizontal spacing) Bias [m/s] Standard deviation [m/s] N – S differences in v (dir. north) 0.019 0.392 E – W differences in u (dir. east) -0.085 0.229 N – S & E – W differences in w (dir. up) 0.048 0.230 Biases are all <0.1 m/s and therefore neglectable compared to the error of the LiDAR. Standard deviations are higher and can be explained as follows. In the N-S direction, which is the prevailing direction, you can expect larger changes as you increase horizontal spacing as there is a strong channeling effect. Yet, still errors are within < 0.5m/s which is less than the LiDAR standard measuring error. For E-W direction, the error at lower height is slightly bigger which is likely due to surface effects. Our CFD simulations don't include thermal winds such as katabatic and anabatic winds due to thermal forcing, therefore errors may be a bit bigger in reality. But still far within reason to assume homogeneity. Finally, there is a small vertical wind speed error as the pass winds have to go up over the pass and then down again. However, with the angle of the laser at 28° from the vertical, the effective error is halved ($\sin(28^\circ) \approx 0.5$) and therefore also well within reason. As the manuscript contains already a lot of tables and information, we have opted to not show this table in the manuscript and rather address this issue in the following subsection:

Addressed in the manuscript as such: *“LiDAR horizontal flow homogeneity assumption In complex terrain, concerns may arise regarding the applicability of Doppler wind LiDARs, as horizontal flow inhomogeneities can violate the homogeneity assumption underlying the retrieval of vertical wind profiles. The WindCube V2.1 profiler employs four beams inclined 28° from the vertical, corresponding to a horizontal separation of approximately 100 m between opposing beams at 100 m height. To evaluate potential impacts of horizontal inhomogeneity, we analysed CFD simulations across representative distances of 100 m (at 100 m height) and 300 m (at 300 m height) in all four cardinal directions. This shows that the mean biases in all wind components remain below 0.1 ms⁻¹, which is negligible relative to the intrinsic measurement uncertainty of the LiDAR. Standard deviations are generally below 0.5 ms⁻¹, with slightly larger values in the north–south direction, attributable to valley channeling, and in the east–west direction near the surface, likely related to surface effects. Although the CFD simulations do not represent thermally driven flows such as katabatic or anabatic winds, which may increase variability in reality, the observed deviations are on the order of the intrinsic error of the LiDAR, thus supporting the validity of the horizontal homogeneity assumption. Consequently, LiDAR-derived vertical profiles can be interpreted without additional corrections.”*

1. Based on the locations where the wind lidar measurements were acquired and the examined wind direction sectors, I imagine that at least part of the wind lidar measurements are biased by the wake generated by the wind turbines.

Indeed we do observe some wind profiles in the LiDAR data, particularly for Northerly winds incident on Turbine 2 going to LiDAR 9, that would fit wake distortion. However, this is not a problem to our methods, but rather a feature of the sequential LiDAR transect. We do not use the LiDAR data to create matches, rather we use the matches to show off LiDAR profiles to visualize the transect 3D wind profile. Since wake distortion is an inherent part of the 3D wind field captured along the transect, its presence helps illustrate the spatial extent of the wake, specifically where it emerges and where it dissipates. The CFD simulations in HICAR do not include the wind turbines and thus also do not suffer from this during the matching algorithm.

1. Furthermore, the quality of the figures and the use of certain references should be improved/corrected (for example the reference [10] is not presenting a validation of a CFD simulation). Therefore, I unfortunately think that the article cannot be considered for indexing in its current version.

We have addressed figure quality and said reference.

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Report 12 February 2025

<https://doi.org/10.21956/openreseurope.20665.r49933>

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Shengming Tang

Shanghai Typhoon Institute of China Meteorological Administration, Shanghai, China

In this study, a deployment method called sequential wind-Doppler LiDAR deployment is introduced. This method proposes a matching algorithm that can group wind profiles among different LiDARs. The proposed deployment method is novel and practical because only a single wind-Doppler LiDAR is needed to construct the three-dimensional wind field instead of multiple synchronized LiDARs. This is an important work for the observational study of the near-surface wind field and the design and operation of wind power generation in mountainous areas. The structure is well designed, the method is innovative, and the analysis is detailed, comprehensive and thorough, with its conclusions are adequately supported by the results. Although this work has good academic and engineering merits, some issues are still needed to be addressed before publication.

1. Table 1: Please explain clearly how to understand the values of Easting (m) and Northing (m)? If a map projection is used, please explain it in the main text.
2. As shown in Figure 11, for northerly wind, the wind direction of L4 rotates clockwise with the increase of height. However, the wind direction of L8 rotates anticlockwise with the increasing height, which is not consistent with the common sense that the wind direction rotates clockwise with the increasing height in the northern hemisphere. Please explain

why.

3. Page 16: Turbulence kinetic energy (TKE) k exhibits bi-modal distributions. What is the meaning of 'bi-modal'?
4. Page 16, Equation 8: The authors assume that the mean wind speed is symmetrical until the second order (e.g. normal distribution). Actually, it is easy to verify whether the wind speed is normally distributed when having the raw data. Please provide the relevant verification process and statistical results.
5. Figures 7, 9, 10, 11 are blurry, please increase the figure resolution.

Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it cite the current literature?

Yes

Is the study design appropriate and does the work have academic merit?

Yes

Are sufficient details of methods and analysis provided to allow replication by others?

Yes

If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate?

Yes

Are all the source data underlying the results available to ensure full reproducibility?

Yes

Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the results?

Yes

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Boundary layer meteorology

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however I have significant reservations, as outlined above.

Author Response 11 Nov 2025

Brandon van Schaik

[Shengming Tang](#)

1. Table 1: Please explain clearly how to understand the values of Easting (m) and Northing (m)? If a map projection is used, please explain it in the main text.

Addressed in the manuscript as such: "Table 1. Instrumentation and data availability. Easting and Northing coordinates in the Swiss Coordinate system LV95 (EPSG:2056)."

- As shown in Figure 11, for northerly wind, the wind direction of L4 rotates clockwise with the increase of height. However, the wind direction of L8 rotates anticlockwise with the increasing height, which is not consistent with the common sense that the wind direction rotates clockwise with the increasing height in the northern hemisphere. Please explain why.

Coriolis forces don't act on this scale (~1km). The forces of the topography greatly outweigh any other apparent rotational forces. The Coriolis acceleration is defined as: $\mathbf{a} = -2\boldsymbol{\omega} \times \mathbf{v}$, $a \leq 2\omega v$
 $\vec{a} = -2(\vec{\omega} \times \vec{v})$, $|\vec{a}| \leq 2|\vec{\omega}||\vec{v}|$ Where the second equation holds as the rotational vector

omega and velocity vector are always perpendicular or very close to perpendicular. With omega pointing to the geometric south pole, and in the maximum acceleration case, the wind pointing true east or true west, we find the maximum possible acceleration in a clockwise direction. Earth rotates at $\omega = 2\pi \text{ rad/day} \cdot \frac{24 \text{ h}}{24 \text{ day}} \cdot \frac{60 \text{ min}}{\text{h}} \cdot \frac{60 \text{ sec}}{\text{min}} = 7.27 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ rad/s}$

$$|\vec{\omega}| = \frac{2\pi \text{ rad/day}}{24 \frac{\text{h}}{\text{day}} \cdot 60 \frac{\text{min}}{\text{h}} \cdot 60 \frac{\text{sec}}{\text{min}}} = 7.27 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ rad/s}$$

For the maximum wind speed of $v = 25 \text{ m/s}$

$|\vec{v}| = 25 \frac{\text{m}}{\text{s}}$, then $a_{\text{max}} = 3.64 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ m/s}^2$, $|\vec{a}|_{\text{max}} = 3.64 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ m/s}^2$, which over the longest distance we have measured over the pass of approximately 1500m, would result in $1.5 \text{ km} \cdot 3.64 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ m/s}^2 = 0.28 \text{ m/s}$

$\frac{1.5 \text{ km}}{25 \frac{\text{m}}{\text{s}}} \cdot 3.64 \cdot 10^{-3} \frac{\text{m}}{\text{s}^2} = 0.28 \text{ m/s}$, of perpendicular wind speed

deviation. Which equates to a rotation of $8.73 \text{ mrad} = 0.50^\circ$. In fact, this rotation is independent of wind speed v , thus under no wind speeds could this deviation be greater than 0.50° . We can conclude from this that the Coriolis force is of negligible influence, and the topographic channelling forces are of much greater effect. **Addressed in the manuscript as such:** "This veering effect can not be explained by any other apparent forces on the wind such as the Coriolis force which actually act in the opposite direction. In fact, the maximum veering that can be introduced by the Coriolis effect over the Gotthard upper plateau, approximately 1500m in length, is 0.50° , independent of wind speed. This is far below the veering observed by the channelling effect created by the topography."

- Page 16: Turbulence kinetic energy (TKE) k exhibits bi-modal distributions. What is the meaning of 'bi-modal'?

A bi-modal distribution is a probability distribution with two modes. We can separate these two distributions, with different modes, by considering northerly and southerly winds separately as they exhibit very different characteristics when considering the turbulence kinetic energy statistics. **Addressed in the manuscript as such:** "Turbulence kinetic energy (TKE) k (Equation 6), equation 5) exhibits bi-modal distributions where northerly and southerly winds exhibit very different TKE characteristics,. This bi-model distribution is similar to the wind speed, along the LiDAR transect as shown in Figure 14"

- Page 16, Equation 8: The authors assume that the mean wind speed is symmetrical until the second order (e.g. normal distribution). Actually, it is easy to verify whether the wind speed is normally distributed when having the raw data. Please provide the relevant verification process and statistical results.

Thank you for this very interesting suggestion. We actually refer to the *wind deviations from the mean* being normally distribution (symmetrical until the second order), but we assume that we refer to the same principle here. We verified with our 1-second resolution wind data

measured by the LiDAR throughout the campaign. We observe that these deviations from the mean are actually not perfectly normally distributed, but is still symmetrical to second order. There exist other symmetric and non-skewed distribution that are symmetrical until the second order, if we fit our data with the normal distribution we observe that the tails are too heavy to create a good fit. Instead, a student-t function fit turns out to address these issues with a coefficient of $v=2.88\pm.02$, $R^2=0.9958$, $RMSE=0.0467ms$

$v = 2.88 \pm .02, R^2 = 0.9958, RMSE = 0.0467 \frac{m}{s}$. Based on this, we can still continue with the same equation 8, where we can now determine the mean horizontal deviation σ

$$\sigma_{horz} = \sqrt{\frac{v}{v-2}} = 1.81$$

Which seems to be to be independent of height. This proves that our rough upperbound still holds. **Addressed in the manuscript as such:** "The difference in power due to this non-linearity is given in 8: $P_{turbulence}=(P(v+\sigma_{horz})+P(v-\sigma_{horz}))/2-P(v)=3/2 \rho A v \sigma_{horz}^2 > 0$ (8) It should be noted that only a part of this turbulence kinetic energy can be transferred to the blades and therefore this value can only be used as an upper-bound. Additionally, this equation assumes that the wind speed deviations to the mean wind speed are symmetrical until the second order, the turbulence power can be considered only as a rough upper-bound to the influence of turbulence on the wind turbine performance. The assumption that the wind speed deviations from the mean is symmetrical to the second order can be validated by considering the 1-second wind speed data measured by the WindCube throughout the campaign. The distribution is symmetrical to the second order and can be fitted with a student-t distribution which exhibits these symmetries, with $v=2.88\pm0.02$, $R^2=0.9958$."

1. Figures 7, 9, 10, 11 are blurry, please increase the figure resolution.

We have addressed figure quality.

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Report 11 February 2025

<https://doi.org/10.21956/openreseurope.20665.r50315>

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Norman Wildmann

Institut für Physik der Atmosphäre, Oberpfaffenhofen, Germany

Van Schaik et al. present an experimental study which utilizes one lidar of type Windcube v2.1 to measure wind profiles at an Alpine pass at different locations. The topic is relevant, since complex terrain flow effects are critical for wind energy siting and many uncertainties remain. I disagree with the authors that their method of sequential lidar scans was shown to be effective for site assessment in this study. The study touches a lot of interesting topics, but lacks a clear focus and

in depth analyses of specific results. It is shooting very high with very general goals, but cannot convincingly show the value of the results. I recommend to reconsider the goals, restructure and resubmit a more focused study which can be backed up with the measurements that are present. General and specific comments are given below. I recommend to reject the manuscript at this point.

General comments

- It should be made more clear in the introduction what the actual goal is of the measurements. You could describe what is the standard procedure for WEA, how long the requirements are for instrument deployment and statistics of wind sectors to benchmark your results with. If wind resource assessment is the goal, then I get the impression that the database is much too small and the sequential lidar transects fails to provide the necessary information. If the goal is to study specific flow conditions, I would expect more of a focus on specific situations and some numerical simulations to accompany the measurements.
- The experimental setup is flawed from my perspective because there is no reference to benchmark the results with. I think it would have been important to have at least one lidar continuously at one position. A CFD model to simulate specific wind conditions and check if matching different situations is appropriate could also be applied, but is not provided. Atmospheric stability is not measured at all, but is crucial.
- The method section is not well introduced and the purpose for the whole wind speed matching remains very unclear when it is first introduced and is not well explained. The equations are unprecise and variable names are not well introduced.
- The way I understand the matching algorithm, two situations are considered the same if wind vectors are within a certain margin, but that is not a full description of the flow.
- Figures are of bad quality (low resolution). The captions are not describing the figures well.
- Equations are not well explained and variables not described.
- The structure of the manuscript is not consistent jumping back and forth between methods, results, definition of goals. There is no clear story-line.
- Many statements and references are unprecise and sometimes even wrong. The authors should carefully revise the text.
- Drawing conclusions from wind profiles that are put together from different days and conditions, just matched by wind speed at hub height can be extremely misleading.
- The manuscript is provided in a format which is hard to review (2 columns, no line numbers, etc.). That is maybe not the authors fault, but editors should consider to change the format.

Specific comments:

p.4, paragraph 1: There are clear definitions for terrain complexity in the IEC 61400. It is probably good to elude a bit on that in the introduction and make clear that the complexity in this study is of the highest complexity (I assume)

p.4, paragraph 1: "influencing the performance of wind turbines by reducing or augmenting their efficiency". That sentence is not giving much information

p.4, 2nd column 2nd paragraph: "airborne lidar" - that is not correct. There was no airborne lidar measuring wind transects across the valley at Perdigao.

p.4, 2nd column 2nd paragraph: simulations cannot prove the validity of lidar measurements and were not used for that purpose in the referenced studies.

p.4, 2nd column 3rd paragraph: WEAs operate lidars to perform WEA? that is a weird construction

p.7, 2nd column "Lidar details": The range gate increments was already introduced in the chapter before. It may make sense to move this section before the explanation of the sequential Instrumentation overview.

p.9, 1st column, 2nd paragraph: why is the temperature sensor at 1m? Usually 2m is a

standardized height for such measurements.

p.9, Eq.1 etc.: At this point in the manuscript it is unclear why you want to calculate the difference of all 10-minute wind speeds for the five turbines

p.10, Fig.6: the resolution of this figure is very low and texts are hard to read.

p.11, right column, 2nd paragraph: pressure, temperature and humidity are not shown in this manuscript though, right? Which instrumentation is used to check it? Are there any measures for stability? How the flow develops along the transect is surely dependent on stability.

p.11, right column, "Results": are Fig.6&7 not already results?

p.11, right column, last paragraphs: why are these paragraphs italic? where do they belong to?

p.13, Table 3: why not show the distributions?

p.11, "above rated wind speed": the wind roses do not distinguish between above and below rated wind speed, the upper bin is $>8\text{m/s}$, but rated wind speed is 11m/s .

p.12, Figure 8: What are turbines A-E? So far they were referenced with numbers 1-5 or T1-T5. Please be consistent or describe in the caption.

p.13, Figure 9: The caption should be more descriptive about what the colors and arrows mean.

p.13, right column, first paragraph: If you see a flow acceleration between the position, how can you be sure that acceleration effects are not also present at hub height and would this not be a problem for the wind matching? You actually match conditions which are very different.

p.14, Figure 11: The figure clearly shows that for positions L4 and L8 there was strong shear and veer, thus a very different flow condition than for the other positions. How can you put these conditions together? It does not make sense.

p.14, right column, last paragraph: I cannot believe that the shear and veer at a specific location is independent of atmospheric stability.

p.15, Table 4: the table shows that wind profiles of early morning, early afternoon and late afternoon are mixed.

p.17, Fig.14: what are the axis of those TKE distribution plots?

p.16, "Turbulence kinetic energy": This Section is premature. You cannot make statistics of TKE with this database and calculate effects on power production the way it is done here. The references are wrong too. Reference 8 does not provide Eq. 8. I recommend to have a close look at the IEC 61400 standards.

p.19, Fig.15: What is the normalized power production. There should be an equation somewhere.

p.19, "Sequential vs. Synchronized": This section does not give any new information compared to the introduction and an actual comparison cannot be made, because data from synchronized lidars is not available in this campaign.

p.19, "Conclusion": "a novel method for high-resolution, three-dimensional wind profile measurements" - I disagree. The data presented here is not "high-resolution three-dimensional" It is standard wind profiles with Windcube v2.1. for short time periods at different locations.

p.20, second paragraph: I disagree that the matching algorithm is successful. The analyses show that just matching the wind speed at hub height is not enough to describe a common flow situation in such complex environment. Actually it is misleading to suggest it does.

Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it cite the current literature?

No

Is the study design appropriate and does the work have academic merit?

No

Are sufficient details of methods and analysis provided to allow replication by others?

Yes

If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate?

Partly

Are all the source data underlying the results available to ensure full reproducibility?

Partly

Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the results?

No

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: boundary-layer meteorology, lidar measurements, complex terrain, wind energy

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to state that I do not consider it to be of an acceptable scientific standard, for reasons outlined above.

Author Response 11 Nov 2025

Brandon van Schaik

Norman Wildmann

- It should be made more clear in the introduction what the actual goal is of the measurements. You could describe what is the standard procedure for WEA, how long the requirements are for instrument deployment and statistics of wind sectors to benchmark your results with. If wind resource assessment is the goal, then I get the impression that the database is much too small and the sequential lidar transects fails to provide the necessary information. If the goal is to study specific flow conditions, I would expect more of a focus on specific situations and some numerical simulations to accompany the measurements.

R: The section title of Methods was misplaced in this draft which meant that a large part of the introduction was actually displayed as the start of the introduction. We have indicated this to be changed to the correct position in the next iteration. Regarding the clarity of the goals, it is **addressed in the manuscript as such:** "This work serves as a proof of concept and as a preliminary showcase of the unique data sets and analyses that are unlocked by the sequential LiDAR experimental methodology, enabling the high-resolution study of the three-dimensional wind over the entire wind park domain.". In response to this comment, and those made by another reviewer, we have complemented the LiDAR observations with additional CFD simulations covering the full 3-month campaign period and the entire mountain pass. These simulations provide spatially and temporally continuous wind fields that support the short-term measurements. Specifically, we have identified 8 characteristic features including, global horizontal irradiance, atmospheric stability, vertical shear magnitude, variance of the vertical turbulence, an average of the transect wind field, and the synoptic wind at 5km. To this end, the Methodology section is completely overhauled

and Results updated accordingly. We believe this addresses the reviewer's concern by providing a more complete picture of the wind conditions across all sites.

- The experimental setup is flawed from my perspective because there is no reference to benchmark the results with. I think it would have been important to have at least one lidar continuously at one position. A CFD model to simulate specific wind conditions and check if matching different situations is appropriate could also be applied, but is not provided. Atmospheric stability is not measured at all, but is crucial.

R: Thanks to your suggestions we have opted to provide additional CFD simulations to help contextualize the turbine wind vector matching algorithm. We have updated the matching algorithm as elaborated in the previous comments. We refer to the Methodology section of the manuscript for the detailed overview of the 8 characteristic features that are now implemented.

- The method section is not well introduced and the purpose for the whole wind speed matching remains very unclear when it is first introduced and is not well explained.

R: The equations are unprecise and variable names are not well introduced. To make this transition to the Methodology more clear, as well as to introduce the idea of the wind speed matching immediately, we have moved the LiDAR details to the instrumentation section. We have improved equations and variables and completely overhauled the Methodology section to include the 8 CFD characteristic features. We believe this overhaul has greatly improved the flow of this section.

- The way I understand the matching algorithm, two situations are considered the same if wind vectors are within a certain margin, but that is not a full description of the flow.

R: We have updated the matching algorithm as elaborated in the previous comments. We refer to the Methodology section of the manuscript for the detailed overview of the 8 characteristic features that are now implemented.

- Figures are of bad quality (low resolution). The captions are not describing the figures well.

R: Figure quality has been addressed. We are limited to 15 words per caption by the journal, we have optimised captions within this limit.

- Equations are not well explained and variables not described.

R: We have checked all equations and verified that variables are introduced and described.

- The structure of the manuscript is not consistent jumping back and forth between methods, results, definition of goals. There is no clear story-line.

R: We have updated the matching algorithm as elaborated in the previous comments. We refer to the Methodology section of the manuscript for the detailed overview of the 8 characteristic features that are now implemented.

- Many statements and references are unprecise and sometimes even wrong. The authors should carefully revise the text.

R: We assume said statements and references are described in the reviewer's specific comments. We have addressed those below.

- Drawing conclusions from wind profiles that are put together from different days and conditions, just matched by wind speed at hub height can be extremely misleading.

R: We have updated the matching algorithm as elaborated in the previous comments. We refer to the Methodology section of the manuscript for the detailed overview of the 8 characteristic features that are now implemented.

- The manuscript is provided in a format which is hard to review (2 columns, no line numbers, etc.). That is maybe not the authors fault, but editors should consider to change the format. **R:** We thank the reviewer for pointing this out. The manuscript format is determined by the journal's submission system, and unfortunately we do not have direct control over line numbering or layout. We trust that the editorial office will take this into consideration.

Specific comments:

p.4, paragraph 1: There are clear definitions for terrain complexity in the IEC 61400. It is probably good to elude a bit on that in the introduction and make clear that the complexity in this study is of the highest complexity (I assume)

R: We appreciate the reviewer's suggestion. While the IEC 61400 provides clear definitions for terrain complexity, it is not an open-access document, and therefore we have chosen not to cite it directly. Nonetheless, we agree that the terrain in our study area qualifies as highly complex according to commonly used classifications. We have clarified this in the revised introduction to better frame the context of our work, without relying on proprietary standards. **Addressed in the manuscript as such:** "The Gotthard Wind Park can be categorised as the highest degree of complex terrain for wind energy development, characterised by large elevation changes, up- and downwind valleys and steep escarpments within the wind park itself."

p.4, paragraph 1: "influencing the performance of wind turbines by reducing or augmenting their efficiency". That sentence is not giving much information

R: Addressed in the manuscript as such: "influencing the performance of the wind turbine by the non-idealised wind flow into the turbine."

p.4, 2nd column 2nd paragraph: "airborne lidar" - that is not correct. There was no airborne lidar measuring wind transects across the valley at Perdigao.

R: We thank the reviewer for catching this mistake. The reference to "airborne lidar" was incorrect and has been removed. It was a confusion with the airborne surface scanning LiDAR used at Perdigão.

p.4, 2nd column 2nd paragraph: simulations cannot prove the validity of lidar measurements and were not used for that purpose in the referenced studies.

R: Addressed in the manuscript as such: "establishing the use of LiDAR measurements as a valid wind assessment tool over a wide range of spatial resolutions."

p.4, 2nd column 3rd paragraph: WEAs operate lidars to perform WEA? that is a weird construction

R: "WEAs rarely operate more than one LiDAR to perform a wind energy assessment."

Replaced by: "WEA studies rarely operate more than one LiDAR"

p.7, 2nd column "Lidar details": The range gate increments was already introduced in the chapter before. It may make sense to move this section before the explanation of the sequential Instrumentation overview.

R: Thank you for the helpful suggestion, we have adopted this in the revision.

p.9, 1st column, 2nd paragraph: why is the temperature sensor at 1m? Usually 2m is a standardized height for such measurements.

R: Out of practical reasons this was done. A one metre rebar pole could be easily hammered into the soil. Longer poles to mount the sensor at 2m would require guywires which was not always possible in the terrain. Since the LiDAR was moved every week, this was not practical. Since the surface topography is free of brushes and rocks, this difference should not impact the variances in the temperature readings much. Particularly since we average over 10min intervals. Since the temperature is only used for air density calculations in which the temperature only has a small sensitivity, we do not see a reason to distrust the accuracy of this data. **Addressed in the manuscript as such:** "A radiation-shielded combined pressure, temperature, and humidity sensor was placed near the LiDAR 1 m above the ground which is solely used to calculate the local air density."

p.9, Eq.1 etc.: At this point in the manuscript it is unclear why you want to calculate the difference of all 10-minute wind speeds for the five turbines

R: With the additional CFD simulations methods in the manuscript, this has been addressed accordingly. We have also introduced the goals more clearly, and earlier in the manuscript.

p.10, Fig.6: the resolution of this figure is very low and texts are hard to read.

R: All figures have been replaced with higher-resolution versions in the revised manuscript. In addition, Figure 6 is no longer included, as it became irrelevant following the revisions to the Methodology section and has been removed.

p.11, right column, 2nd paragraph: pressure, temperature and humidity are not shown in this manuscript though, right? Which instrumentation is used to check it? Are there any measures for stability? How the flow develops along the transect is surely dependent on stability.

R: We only use pressure temperature and humidity to calculate the average air density over the whole campaign. We mention the existence of this sensor as it is included in the data set that is co-published with this paper. The sensor in use is the standard PTH sensor provided by VAISALA for the WindCube v2.1. More details are now given in the instrumentation table (Table 1). Atmospheric stability is now addressed with CFD simulations. We refer the reviewer to our reply of his first comment as well as the Methodology section of the revised manuscript for the full details.

p.11, right column, "Results": are Fig.6&7 not already results?

R: These figure have become irrelevant following the revisions to the Methodology section and have since been removed.

p.11, right column, last paragraphs: why are these paragraphs italic? where do they belong

to?

R: We thank the reviewer for noting this editing error. The paragraphs are now placed correctly in the revised manuscript.

p.13, Table 3: why not show the distributions?

R: In our view, the distributions are not directly relevant to the goals of the study. Presenting the results in tabular form provides a more space-efficient and quantitative summary, allowing readers to readily compare the two wind directions as well as reproduce/refer to the data immediately.

p.11, "above rated wind speed": the wind roses do not distinguish between above and below rated wind speed, the upper bin is >8m/s, but rated wind speed is 11m/s.

R: Excellent suggestion, the wind roses are updated to reflect the different stages in the E-92 power curve, and the figure has been updated.

p.12, Figure 8: What are turbines A-E? So far they were referenced with numbers 1-5 or T1-T5. Please be consistent or describe in the caption.

R: Combined with the previous comment, we have adapted this as well in the figure.

p.13, Figure 9: The caption should be more descriptive about what the colors and arrows mean.

R: We are limited to 15 words per figure/table caption by the journal regulations. We have described this in more detail in the text. We have also added a legend to explain the difference in colours. Besides, this figure has been replaced due to the improved methodology as suggested in your earlier comments. We refer the reviewer to the Transect wind profile evolution and Wind shear and veer subsections in the results for our improved results.

p.13, right column, first paragraph: If you see a flow acceleration between the position, how can you be sure that acceleration effects are not also present at hub height and would this not be a problem for the wind matching? You actually match conditions which are very different. **R:** We have updated the matching algorithm as elaborated in the previous comments. We refer to the Methodology section of the manuscript for the detailed overview of the 8 characteristic features that are now implemented. This flow acceleration can now be identified using by CFD simulation characteristic features: "Vertical shear magnitude", "Variance of the vertical turbulence", and "Transect-averaged wind". We refer the reviewer to the Transect wind profile evolution and Wind shear and veer subsections in the results for our improved results.

p.14, Figure 11: The figure clearly shows that for positions L4 and L8 there was strong shear and veer, thus a very different flow condition than for the other positions. How can you put these conditions together? It does not make sense.

R: We have updated the matching algorithm as elaborated in the previous comments. We refer to the Methodology section of the manuscript for the detailed overview of the 8 characteristic features that are now implemented. This shear/veer concern can now be identified using by CFD simulation characteristic features: "Vertical shear magnitude", "Variance of the vertical turbulence", "Global Horizontal Irradiance", "Atmospheric stability", and "Synoptic wind at 5km". We refer the reviewer to the Transect wind profile evolution

and Wind shear and veer subsections in the results for our improved results.

p.14, right column, last paragraph: I cannot believe that the shear and veer at a specific location is independent of atmospheric stability.

R: We have updated the matching algorithm as elaborated in the previous comments. We refer to the Methodology section of the manuscript for the detailed overview of the 8 characteristic features that are now implemented. This shear/veer and atmospheric stability concern can now be identified using by CFD simulation characteristic features: "Vertical shear magnitude", "Variance of the vertical turbulence", and "Atmospheric stability". We refer the reviewer to the Transect wind profile evolution and Wind shear and veer subsections in the results for our improved results.

p.15, Table 4: the table shows that wind profiles of early morning, early afternoon and late afternoon are mixed.

R: We have updated the matching algorithm as elaborated in the previous comments. We refer to the Methodology section of the manuscript for the detailed overview of the 8 characteristic features that are now implemented. This time of day mixing can now be identified using by CFD simulation characteristic features: "Global Horizontal Irradiance", and "Atmospheric Stability" We have consequently updated the table to address the stricter matching protocol discussed in the overhauled Methodology section.

p.17, Fig.14: what are the axis of those TKE distribution plots?

R: We have revised the captions to clarify that the plots represent probability density functions of the TKE. The as the exact values of TKE are not directly relevant for our conclusions, and for clarity we therefore choose to not include x ticks or y ticks. Since our caption size is limited, we have updated the manuscript section in which the figure is first referred to as shown below. The plots are intended to highlight relative differences, and since all TKE distributions share identical x-limits, they can be visually intercompared as discussed in the manuscript. **Addressed in the manuscript as such:** "This bi-model distribution is similar to the wind speed, along the LiDAR transect as shown in Figure 12. In these figures, the red lines represent the probability density functions of the TKE, while the blue vertical lines indicate the mean TKE, allowing for a visual identification of where turbulence is strongest along the transect."

p.16, "Turbulence kinetic energy": This Section is premature. You cannot make statistics of TKE with this database and calculate effects on power production the way it is done here. The references are wrong too. Reference 8 does not provide Eq. 8. I recommend to have a close look at the IEC 61400 standards.

R: We thank the reviewer for this valuable comment. We have revised the section to clarify that our analysis is not intended as a full turbulence kinetic energy (TKE) assessment, but rather as a simplified approach to provide a rough upper bound on the potential influence of turbulence on turbine performance. We now emphasize that Eq. (8) is a first-order approximation based on the curvature of the power curve and assumes symmetric fluctuations up to second order. Furthermore, we have verified the applicability of Eq. (8) using our 1-second LiDAR data, which shows that the deviations from the mean are approximately symmetric and can be fitted by a Student-t distribution. This supports the use of Eq. (8) as a conservative upper-bound rather than a precise quantification. Finally, we have corrected the references and added a note pointing the reader to the IEC 61400

standards, which provide the proper framework for turbulence intensity and load assessments. **Addressed in the manuscript as such:** "Equation 8 provides a first-order estimate of how turbulence around the mean affect turbine power output: Equation 8 $P_{turbulence} = P(v + \sigma_{horz}) + P(v - \sigma_{horz}) - P(v) = 3/2 \rho A v \sigma_{horz}^2 > 0$

$$P_{turbulence} = \frac{P(v + \sigma_{horz}) + P(v - \sigma_{horz})}{2} - P(v) = \frac{3}{2} \rho A v \sigma_{horz}^2 > 0$$

However, the actual effect of turbulence is governed by the curvature of the turbine power curve: In convex sections of the power curve, positive and negative fluctuations are weighted asymmetrically, leading to a net increase in power relative to the mean wind speed. Whereas in concave sections, the reverse occurs and fluctuations produce a net decrease in power. Therefore Equation 8 represents only a rough upper-bound to the influence of turbulence on power production. It does not account for the changing curvature of the real power curve, nor for higher-order asymmetries in the wind speed distribution. For a full quantification, we refer the reader to a work that integrates the measured wind speed probability density function and other vertical variations with the actual turbine power curve as referred to in international standards. Furthermore, we have validated the assumption of second-order symmetry in the wind speed variations measured the Doppler wind LiDAR. The 1-second wind speed data from the WindCube during the campaign shows that the deviations from the mean are not perfectly normally distributed. They rather remain symmetric up to second order and can be fitted optimally with a Student-t distribution ($v = 2.88 \pm 0.02$, $R^2 = 0.996$), which captures the heavy tails observed. From this the mean horizontal deviation can be expressed as $\sigma_{horz} = v / (v - 2) = 1.81$

$v = 2.88 \pm 0.02, R^2 = 0.996$), which captures the heavy tails observed. From this the mean horizontal deviation can be expressed as $\sigma_{horz} = v / (v - 2) = 1.81$

$\sigma_{horz} = \sqrt{v / (v - 2)} = 1.81$, Which seems to be independent of height. Which consequently validates that the rough upper-bound still holds."

p.19, Fig.15: What is the normalized power production. There should be an equation somewhere.

R: Addressed in the manuscript as such: "The power production is normalised to 7 ms^{-1} by the cubic relation between power and wind speed in this range with Equation 9. Equation 9 $P_{normalised} = P(v) \frac{C_p(7 \text{ ms}^{-1}) (7 \text{ ms}^{-1})^3}{C_p(v) v^3}, 4 \text{ ms}^{-1} \leq v \leq 10 \text{ ms}^{-1}$

$$P_{normalised} = P(v) \frac{C_p(7 \text{ ms}^{-1}) (7 \text{ ms}^{-1})^3}{C_p(v) v^3}, 4 \text{ ms}^{-1} \leq v \leq 10 \text{ ms}^{-1}$$

p.19, "Sequential vs. Synchronized": This section does not give any new information compared to the introduction and an actual comparison cannot be made, because data from synchronized lidars is not available in this campaign.

R: We have conducted additional CFD simulations to address this concern, as outlined in our earlier responses. We believe that these methodological adaptations improve the robustness of the results and provide sufficient support for our conclusions in this section.

p.19, "Conclusion": "a novel method for high-resolution, three-dimensional wind profile measurements" - I disagree. The data presented here is not "high-resolution three-dimensional" It is standard wind profiles with Windcube v2.1. for short time periods at different locations.

R: We thank the reviewer for this comment. While we agree that standard WindCube v2.1 instruments provide vertical wind profiles at single locations, our methodology goes beyond this typical use. By deploying the lidar sequentially along a dense transect with 150 m horizontal spacing and 10–20 m vertical resolution, we obtain a high-resolution, three-dimensional reconstruction of the wind field across complex terrain. Something that cannot be achieved with a single lidar in a fixed location. Furthermore, the newly added CFD simulations now support and address the reviewer's concerns about temporal discontinuity and the matching algorithm. Therefore, we believe that the description of the method as "high-resolution, three-dimensional wind profile measurements" is appropriate in the context of this study.

p.20, second paragraph: I disagree that the matching algorithm is successful. The analyses show that just matching the wind speed at hub height is not enough to describe a common flow situation in such complex environment. Actually it is misleading to suggest it does.

R: The newly added CFD simulations help address the reviewer's concerns regarding temporal discontinuity and provide validation for the adapted matching algorithm. We therefore consider the revised algorithm to be appropriate and effective for the purposes of this study.

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.
